

Predation increased with the mirid population. It was highest 91 d after transplanting when the mirid population was 1.25/hill (see table). □

Comparison of yellow stem borer (YSB) catch in light traps

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We compared three traps for their relative efficiency in attracting YSB moths at the Tirur Rice Research Station during 1988-89. We used a local bamboo light trap with 40-W incandescent bulb (LBL-T 40 W) and two modified Robinson light traps. One had a 125-W mercury vapor lamp (MRL-T 125 W), and the other a

200-W, incandescent bulb (MRL-T 200 W). Traps were located at least 100 m apart.

The MRL-T 200 W attracted the most moths (13.5 moths/d) and the LBL-T 40

W the least (4.7 moths/d). The MRL-T 125 W captured 34.9% and the MRL-T 200 W, 189.3% more moths than the LBL-T 40 W (see table). Differences were significant. □

Attraction of YSB moths to MRL-T with 2 light intensities and to LBL-T.

Month	Daily catch ^a (no.) of YSB moths		
	MRL-T 125 W	MRL-T 200 W	LBL-T 40 W
Apr 1988	18.6 (1.31)	60.6 (1.79)	42.9 (1.63)
May	9.2 (1.05)	16.8 (1.27)	5.4 (0.87)
Jun	2.0 (0.60)	0.7 (0.44)	0.1 (0.32)
Jul	0.6 (0.42)	1.2 (0.51)	0.0 (0.32)
Aug	0.5 (0.40)	2.6 (0.66)	1.5 (0.54)
Sep	1.3 (0.52)	5.6 (0.88)	0.9 (0.46)
Oct	3.6 (0.75)	6.9 (0.94)	0.5 (0.40)
Nov	0.7 (0.44)	4.5 (0.81)	0.1 (0.32)
Dec	10.4 (1.09)	22.9 (1.39)	0.8 (0.45)
Jan 1989	18.0 (1.30)	28.7 (1.48)	1.7 (0.56)
Feb	2.9 (0.69)	3.7 (0.76)	1.2 (0.51)
Mar	8.16 (1.00)	7.4 (0.97)	0.4 (0.39)
Mean ^b	6.38 (0.801)	13.51 (0.997)	4.67 (0.569)
Increase (%) over LBL-T 40 W	34.9	189.3	-

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values. ^bSignificantly different (p = 0.05) by DMRT.

Integrated pest management—weeds

Weed control in wet seeded rice in Kerala, India

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The majority of farmers in the Kerala rice belt practice wet seeding. We evaluated nine weed control treatments to identify the most suitable method for wet seeded rice. The treatments involved four preemergence herbicides and hand weeding during monsoon (Jun-Oct) and wet season (Nov-Mar) 1988-89.

The field experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. The soil was silty clay. We sowed sprouted MO-6 seeds (115 d) on a puddled field at 100 kg/ha. Fertilizers at 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha and herbicides were applied 6 d after seeding (DAS). Weeds were manually removed at fortnightly intervals to 45 DAS in the weed-free check (WFC),

and to 20 and 40 DAS in plots hand-weeded twice (HWT).

Weed flora at 60 DAS consisted of 22% grasses, 40% sedges, and 32% broadleaf weeds. Dominant weed species were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica*.

Pooled analysis of data showed that interaction between season and treatment was not statistically significant. All weed control treatments significantly reduced weed dry weight/m² compared with the unweeded control (see table).

Grain yields with butachlor were high, and on par with those of WFC and HWT. Its lower dose (1.0 kg ai/ha) was most economic and is best suited to wet seeded rice in Kerala. □

Effect of weed control treatments on wet seeded rice. Kerala, India, 1988-89.^a

Treatment ^b	Dose ^c (kg ai/ha)	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit of weed control (\$/ha)	Cost of weed control (\$/ha)	Marginal benefit-cost ratio
Tridiphane 48 EC	0.4	7.69	2.5	3.7	521	440	26	16.9
Tridiphane 48 EC	0.6	5.40	2.0	3.5	423	342	38	9.0
Butachlor (Thunder) 50 EC	1.0	4.36	2.0	3.4	415	334	15	22.3
Butachlor (Searle) 50 EC	1.0	5.75	2.7	3.5	559	478	15	31.8
Butachlor (Searle) 50 EC	1.5	4.61	2.6	3.0	545	464	22	21.1
Thiobencarb 10 G	1.5	8.91	2.4	2.6	501	420	35	12.0
Weed-free check (WFC)		4.16	2.8	3.6	589	508	101	5.0
Hand weeding twice (HWT)		4.50	2.5	2.8	514	433	70	6.2
Unweeded check		23.12	0.4	1.0	81	-	-	-
LSD (0.05)		4.19	0.4	0.7	-	-	-	-

^a Pooled mean of two seasons. ^b EC = emulsifiable concentrate. G = granule. ^c ai = active ingredient. Costs: tridiphane 48 EC = \$28.67/liter, butachlor (Thunder) and (Searle) 50 EC (products of two companies) = \$6.65/liter, thiobencarb 10 G = \$2.20/kg, grain = \$200/t, straw = \$5/t.